

ROLE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation. In this article, the role of information technologies in education, the quality of lessons and the increase of young people's interest in the field of IT through the use of information technologies in lessons, and the advantages of multimedia tools in education are investigated.

Key words: Information, communication, technology, audio signal, video signal, multimedia, individual, motivation, computer, informatics.

The modern world level of the development of information and communication technologies is such that the creation of a national system compatible with the integration of the infrastructures of the world information space and the national information and computing network in the republic is an important factor in the effectiveness of the national economy, management, science and education. These problems are very complex and at the same time urgent for our republic.

The results of the implementation of economic, structural and other changes currently being carried out depend on how and in what time frame the problems related to informatization are solved in the republic. The creation of electronic educational tools for educational subjects further expands the possibility of using modern information and communication technologies in teaching these subjects. This, in turn, is the main factor of students' in-depth assimilation of knowledge in these subjects and increases the quality and efficiency of education.

The implementation of such efforts will further accelerate the wide application of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process,

equip professors and teachers with advanced pedagogical knowledge and technologies, improve their skills, and use the experience of foreign higher education institutions. provides an opportunity for in-depth study and introduction of their effective methods and tools into our national education system.

Multimedia is a rapidly developing modern information technology. It's distinguishing features include: it integrates different types of information: traditional (text, tables, decorations, etc.),original (speech, music, clips from video films, TV frames, animation, etc.) in one software product.

Such an integration is different devices for registering and displaying information, work at a certain time, unlike text and graphics, which are static by their nature, audio and video signals are viewed only at a certain time interval. will be released.

The speed of the central processor for processing and displaying video and audio information on the computer, the bandwidth of the data transmission bus, the operating and video memory, large-capacity external memory, the size and the speed of exchange of computer input-output channels by approximately two times needs to be increased, a new level of "human-computer" interactive communication, in which the user receives more extensive and comprehensive information during the communication process, which makes it possible to improve the conditions of education, work or recreation.

The gross turnover of multimedia tools in 1981 was 4 billion US dollars, and in 1994 it was 16 billion US dollars. Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine every computer sold without multimedia tools.

Informatics and information technologies, as a fundamental science, deals with the development of a methodology for establishing management processes with information on the basis of computer information systems.

Although the idea of using computers in the educational system appeared much earlier, the use of information technology in all areas of the educational system became more complete after the advent of computers equipped with multimedia

devices. was put into practice. The use of multimedia tools in education provides the following opportunities:

- ensuring the humanization of education;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;
- development of the student's personal qualities (assimilation, thirst for knowledge, independent education, self-education, ability to improve oneself, creative abilities, applying acquired knowledge in practice ability, interest in learning, attitude to work).

According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as the combination of various types of multimedia educational information, interactivity, and flexibility qualities, multimedia is useful and productive education. In technology, multimedia tools are an effective and promising tool (instrument) of education, which provides the teacher with a large-scale array of information, rather than a traditional source of information; visually and harmoniously, not only the text, the use of graphics, diagrams, but also sound, animations, video, etc.; creates an opportunity to select types of information in a sequence in accordance with the level of reception (perception) and logical learning of learners [1.B.3].

Conclusion.

In conclusion, I can say that the use of information technologies has brought great benefits to society and the state. In the age of information technologies of the 21st century in Uzbekistan, the educational process is conducted at a high level by highly educated pedagogues, not only in higher educational institutions, but also in secondary and special educational institutions. The role of information technology is invaluable for making such educational processes more qualitative and interesting. For this reason, it is very important for every pedagogue to know information technology and be able to use information technology.

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